

Effect of the nature of humic substances and ionic strength on the stabilization of colloidal bentonite

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The transport of the colloidal component of river runoff into the marine environment has been poorly studied, although it directly depends on the stability of dispersed systems with increasing salinity. The study of the aggregative stability of clay colloids, which are one of the components of river waters, is important not only as investigation of river water dynamic but also for the study of water treatment conditions. Previously, we demonstrated the ability of humic acids (HA) to stabilize bentonite colloids with increasing salinity (ionic strength) of water in an experiment simulating the mixing zone of river and seawater [1]. The aim of this work was to evaluate the influence of different HA on the stability of colloidal bentonite (CB) at different ionic strength of their solutions.

Bentonite (Oglanli deposit, Tajikistan, fraction $<1 \mu\text{m} >50\%$) was used as a model clay mineral. Coal humic acids (HA-Pow) (Powhumus, Germany), Sakhalinsky humate (SH) (Sakhalinsky Humates, Russia) and Lignohumate (LH) (St. Petersburg, Russia) were used as HA samples.

CB was obtained from the top layer of the solution after settling the bentonite suspension (2 g/L) for 10 days at room temperature (CB particle size is 180-200 nm, zeta potencial -37 mV). Modification of clay particles by HA (10 mg/l) was carried out by their adsorption on clays for 5 days at room temperature. The turbidity of the samples, as a measure of the colloidal stability, was studied with the use of a HI 98713-02 turbidimeter (Hanna, Romania). Drop shape analysis was used for determining the contact angle of the drop on the glass plates as the measure of hydrophilicity of HA. The parameters for comparing the stability of the dispersed system were the time during which the system does not react to the presence of salt or the concentration of salt that causes coagulation over a certain period of time.

It was shown, that as the hydrophilicity of HA increases (determined by the decrease in the contact angle of a water drop on the glass plate modified with HA), their ability to stabilize CB increases. Thus, coagulation of CB modified with SH at a salinity of 17 ‰ occurs only after 60 minutes, whereas the effect of HA-Pow under the same conditions is noticeable after 20 minutes. At the same time the contact angle for SH does not change significantly with increasing HA concentration having value near 28° , whereas for HA-Pow it increases from 28° to 34° , passing through a maximum of 46° . Thus, CB stabilization in mixing zones is influenced not only by the type of HA, but also by their concentration.

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References

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